

Dr. David Render PhD

Fruits and Vegetables Health Medicine Fuel for the Body

4 Healing Natural

By: Dr. David Render

Nutrition Facts

Serving Size oz.
Serving Per Container

Amount Per Serving:

Calories	Calories From Fat	% Daily value*
Total Fat		%
Saturated Fat		%
Trans Fat		
Cholesterol		%
Sodium		%
Total Carbohydrate		%
Dietary Fiber		%
Sugars		
Protein		

*Percent Daily values are based on a 2000 calorie diet. Your daily values may be higher or lower depending on your calorie needs.

Nutrition Facts

Serving Size 10 oz.
Serving Per Container 5

Amount Per Serving

Calories 200 **Calories From Fat 200**

		% Daily value*
Total Fat	10 g	35%
Saturated Fat	1.5g	11%
Trans Fat	0.0 g	
Cholesterol	0 mg	1%
Sodium	210 mg	15%
Total Carbohydrate	15 g	3%
Dietary Fiber	2 g	3%
Sugars	3 g	
Protein	30 g	

Vitamin A	3%	•	Vitamin C	3%
Calcium	6%	•	Iron	6%

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Perfect Hummus

Puree the chickpeas, garlic put herbs on top
and enjoy

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Seeds and Bowl Toppings

Pumpkin Seeds
high in Iron and
Magnesium

Hemp
High in protein

Raisins
High in Copper and
Calories

Almond Butter
High in protein & Zinc

Salad bowl >>>

Tomatoes
Vitamin C & A

Lentils Iron &
Protein

Onions Manganese
Vitamin B6

Kale Vitamin C & A

Vegetable Bowl

Vegetable bowl can have
Rice Red Onion
Beans Tahini
Olives Tomatoes

4Healing

Nitrate Rich Foods

Arugula

Basil

Beets

Cilantro

Rhubarb

**Nitrates bring relaxation to the blood vessels,
improve blood vessels and deliver more oxygen to blood
vessels**

Milk Dairy Free Alternatives

1 cup per serving

Flax

Soy

Oak

Pea

Almond

Coconut

Bananas 101

Prebiotic & High Amount of resistant starch nondigestible fibers maybe harsh on your digestive system

High antioxidant content & digest quickly and sweeter and contain more sugar than green bananas

Greatest nutrients and mineral loss sweet and digestible

Chia pudding

Chia
Seeds

Plant Milk

Toppings

Combine the ingredients & Refrigerate
Overnight Top with Toppings
Enjoy

Rich Protein Vegetables

Green Peas

Alfalfa Sprouts

Brussel Sprouts

Sweet Corn

Collard Greens

Artichokes

Mustard
Greens

Broccoli

Legumes Protein Rich

Kidney Beans

Edamame

Mung Beans

White Beans

Black beans

Chick peas

